

RESEARCH MINI-MUSEUM

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ABSTRACT

This use-case describes the construction of a temporary small-scale museum-like space to display visual research artifacts such as annotated paper prototypes, card sorting, word exercises and interview footage to create new forms of interaction with qualitative research within an organization.

KEYWORDS: *Qualitative research, Research artifacts, Display, Museum, Presentation, Data Dissemination*

INTRODUCTION

As researchers, we have an ever-expanding arsenal of ways to understand people's behavior and attitudes towards Internet services. We can perform usability studies, have participants mark-up paper prototypes, and gather screen shots of the product experience from small "dogfooding" groups, to name just a few methods.

Internet services also need fast research and analysis cycles to allow for rapid product development. As researchers, we are in charge of analyzing more and more qualitative and quantitative data and quickly turning it into actionable insights so that product teams can make informed decisions.

CHALLENGES IN DISSEMINATING RESEARCH

While it's possible to cull many data points into a concise presentation, a lot of valuable detail is banished into the archive section. In addition, the insights are usually only presented to a small group – usually the specific group deciding on product direction.

This is not a new problem: researchers in many different areas of specialization have explored novel ways to disseminate research in a way that preserves detail and encourages access. Some of the successful experiments in qualitative data dissemination incorporate 'the arts' as a method of data shar-

ing. *The 7,024th Patient* [1] used an exhibition of poetry and artistic visuals to immerse audiences in patient experiences. Similarly, *Handle with Care? Women living with Metastatic Breast Cancer* [2] was a research based theatre production aiming to share the lives and concerns of women living with breast cancer.

The above methods though evocative and impactful, are time consuming and thus difficult to implement in a culture that relies on speed and agility: namely Internet services.

This use case explores a way to:

1. *Broaden the reach of UEX research:* Distribute research insights to more people within an organization, not just the specific group deciding product direction.
2. *Preserve detail:* Create a way for research artifacts to be viewed in their raw form.
3. *Craft novel experiences:* Create new interactions with qualitative research within an organization.

OUR PROJECT

The Facebook research team conducted a ten-day study with twelve participants to get foundational insights for a new product we are building. This research included: a set of twelve preliminary interviews to set up the study, asynchronous dscout feedback during the week (dScout is a mobile application that allows research participants to share im-

ages and screenshots on their smartphones directly with a researcher), and follow up interviews where participants responded to design stimuli.

After conducting all of the research sessions, we had a large number of data rich research artifacts:

- 153 snippets of user screenshots and their comments from dscout
- 24 card sorts
- 30 participant annotated paper prototypes
- 12 word exercise sheets
- 12 Likert scales with participant notes and reasons

While analyzing the insights that emerged from all these data points, we wondered whether there was any way that the whole product team, and perhaps even other product teams could look at all these research artifacts in their raw form. We felt that the users' own handwritten comments and feedback, as well as screenshots of the product being used in their day to day lives could be far more impactful than a succinct PowerPoint deck. We wanted to create a format of dissemination that allowed for interaction, slow musing and time for discussion and interpretation.

THE MINI-MUSEUM

Our solution was to construct a small-scale temporary museum, which was focused entirely on our research. Also, since research and development cycles are short, we had to devise a way to put up this exhibition in half a business day. This is how we constructed the space:

- We used an empty workspace with pods of desks to create this museum space.
- *Horizontal display spaces:* Tables served as horizontal display spaces to place the research artifacts. We used these surfaces to display participant card sorting images; paper prototypes with handwritten user annotations, 153 dscout snippet printouts, word exercises and annotated likert scales. We placed large numbers on each desk so that people could navigate the space and follow our narrative (See figure 1.).
- *Vertical display spaces.* We decided to put the high level insights and section titles on vertical displays so that people could see what insights we drew from the raw data in front of them. Since this was a low fidelity set up, we got creative and decided to re-use 'caution wet floor' signs as the vertical display system (See figure 2.).
- *Streaming video:* We used monitors on some of the tables to stream video footage of the research sessions pertinent to the artifact displayed so that the context in which the research artifact was made was clear (See figure 3.).
- Lastly, an event invitation was sent out to the entire product vertical.

Figure 1. The image above illustrates the use of workstations as makeshift display spaces. Here we have displayed annotated paper prototypes.

Figure 2. The image above provides an example of a quick hack for putting together a vertical display for the Research Mini-Museum. This is a 'caution wet floor' sign mounted with paper.

Figure 3. The image above displays our set up with the tables containing images of participant card sorts, and a monitor streaming video of participants sharing their rationale for why they grouped certain cards together.

RESPONSE TO THE MINI-MUSEUM:

- In less than 48 hours, there were 83 RSVPs to the invitations sent out for the Mini-Museum opening. Over the course of the week that the Mini-Museum was up and running, over a 100 people visited the space and interacted with the research artifacts. This was our biggest research turn out yet, and had less notice than any other event. This was also the first time some of the engineers who had been working on this product heard and read feedback from end users. (See figure 4.)
- This format allowed for cross-pollination of research and ideas: we had people from different product groups visit the Mini-Museum and discover ideas that could impact the products they were building. This is often a pain point in large organizations: it is challenging to share research across different product verticals.
- This display format spawned multiple requests to display other research projects in a similar way. In response, our research team plans to socialize this format so that more teams are aware of this option.

Figure 4. The image above displays the Mini-Museum in use.

LEARNINGS FOR FUTURE ITERATIONS:

This new data dissemination system opened up the world of qualitative research to new audiences and some of the research methods we used (such as card sorting and dScout snippets) were not as self-explanatory as we imagined. We noticed that the value of the Mini-Museum was greater when there was a researcher present to answer some of the research methodology related questions.

The artifacts within the Mini-Museum often spawned many ideas and solutions to user stated problems, as well as follow up research questions. In the future, we will work on creating an idea-bank to capture solutions and serve as repositories of ideas for further research.

Lastly, for the long term, we are evaluating whether it would be valuable to turn the Mini-Museum into a permanent space within our organization. This space would be dedicated to sharing different research findings on a regular basis with anyone who is interested in the voice of the end user.

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